

Survey: The Evolution and Applications of Turing Machine

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Abstract—The Turing Machine (TM) is a theoretical model of computational complexity, proposed by Alan Turing in 1936. While not used directly in practical applications, the concepts and principles of TMs have contributed significantly to various fields in computing, including computer Science theory, complexity theory, cryptography, artificial intelligence, compiler construction and computational biology. Despite the numerous applications of the TM model, there are inadequate comprehensive reference surveys of the benchmarking evolutions of this model. In this paper, we present a systematic survey on the evolution of the theory of Turing machines since its inception in 1936 as well as its applications. This paper further analyzes the theory of the Turing Machine and discusses several other variants that are generalizations of the original model. Additionally, it discusses the various applications of Turing Machines in the field of computer science. By understanding the theoretical basis of Turing Machines and their practical applications, researchers and practitioners can continue to make important advancements in a variety of fields

I. INTRODUCTION

A machine can be defined as a mechanically, electrically, or electronically operated device for performing a task. A program on the other hand is a sequence of coded instructions that can be inserted into a machine to control its operation [1], [2]. Alan Turing and Alonzo Church were pioneers in computability theory, with Turing developing the Turing machine (TM) and Church introducing lambda calculus. Their work led to the Church-Turing thesis, a fundamental principle in computer science that states any effectively calculable function can be computed by a TM or equivalent model [3], [4]. Their contributions laid the foundation for modern computer science, artificial intelligence, and complexity theory. The study of formalizing algorithms is known as the theory of computability. Computability theory is concerned with understanding what problems can and cannot be solved by computers or algorithms [3]. In 1936, Alan Turing submitted a solution to the problem of formalizing mathematics and the concept of algorithms in his paper "On Computable Numbers, with an Application to the Entscheidungsproblem". In the paper, he presented the concept of a human computing agent, which he called a "computer", and introduced the intuitive concept of a "function produced by a mechanical process" [5]. Also, he proposed the universal TM which can duplicate any other TM. The

concepts and principles of TMs have contributed significantly to various fields in computing, including computer Science theory, complexity theory, cryptography, artificial intelligence, compiler construction and computational biology. Regardless of the countless merits and potentials of the TM theory in the application space, there exist inadequate systematic reference surveys to update researchers on the evolutions and application trends of this theory benchmarking state-of-the-art. This paper is a review of the literature on the evolution of the theory of TM and discusses the various applications of Turing Machines in the field of computer science. It elaborates on the theory's transformations, development and applications since its inception.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II introduces the formal definition of Turing Machines; Section III discusses the evolution of the Turing Machine theory; Section IV presents the real-world applications of Turing Machines theory in problem-solving spaces and Section V concludes the paper.

II. FORMAL DEFINITION OF TURING MACHINE

A TM is a kind of state machine, which can be any of a finite number of states at any time. A Turing Machine is an accepting device that accepts the languages (recursively enumerable set) generated by type 0 grammars. TM can compute NonContext-Free Language Push Down Automata (PDA) cannot apply. The Instructions for a TM consist of any specified conditions under which the machine will transition from one state to another [6]. As illustrated in Figure 1, a TM consists of a control portion similar to a deterministic PDA or a Finite State Machine and a tape head with alphabets that can be read or updated. The tape head (single or multitape) may move either one step left or right depending on the control. A computation under a TM can either:

- HALT and ACCEPT
- HALT and REJECT
- LOOP (i.e., the machine fails to HALT)

Formally, a TM is defined by a set of 7 tuples $(Q, \Sigma, \Gamma, \delta, q_0, \sqcup, F)$ where:

- $Q \rightarrow$ is a non-empty finite set of states

Fig. 1. Generalized Framework of a TM

- $\Sigma \rightarrow$ is a finite subset of containing symbols that make up the input alphabet
- $\Gamma \rightarrow$ is a finite set of symbols making up the tape alphabet, it includes the blank symbol
- $\delta : Q * \Gamma \rightarrow Q * \Gamma * \{L, R, S\} \rightarrow$ is the transition function, which maps a state and a tape symbol to a new state, a new tape symbol, and a movement of the head to the left (L), right (R), or stay in place (S).
- $q_0 \in Q \rightarrow$ is the initial state
- $\sqcup \rightarrow$ represent blank symbols on the tape
- $F \rightarrow$ is a set of finite states

Consider a simple language whose strings use the input alphabet $\Sigma = \{0, 1\}$. The language can be defined as $L_1 = \{w | w \text{ has even length}\}$. Figure shows the transition states of the TM. *State1* is the state the machine will be in after having seen an even number of characters and *State2* is the state the machine will be in after having seen an odd number of characters.

A. The Operation of a TM

- At each computational step of a TM, the tape head
- Read the current symbol in the current cell
 - Update or Write the same cell
 - Exactly move one cell either LEFT or RIGHT

With the aid of Figure 2, the TM starts in *state1*, scans the input string from left to right, and alternates between *state1* and *state2* as it reads each character, effectively counting the length of the input string. In *state1* if the TM reads symbol 0, it writes 1 and moves the tape head to the right ($0, 1 \rightarrow R$) then transitions to *state2*. Also, in *state2* if the

Fig. 2. TM machine that reads even numbers of 0s and 1s.

TM reads symbol 1, it writes 0 and moves the tape head to the right ($1, 0 \rightarrow R$) then transitions to *state1*. If it reaches a blank symbol while in *state1*, the input string has an even length, and the TM transitions to accept state. If it reaches a blank symbol while in *state2*, the input string has an odd length, and the TM transitions to the reject state. TMs have both accepting final states and rejecting final states. When a Turing machine enters a final state it will stop. If the final state it entered is an accepting state, the machine will accept its original input. If the final state is a rejecting state, the machine rejects its input.

Figure 3 shows the tape of the machine reading the symbol

Fig. 3. Turing Machine reading the symbol '1' on a tape

0 or 1. The triangle indicates the head of the machine. To the left of the tape head are symbols 0, 1, 0, 1... that have been written onto the tape. After writing a symbol, the tap head moves to the right and reads the next symbol.

III. EVOLUTION OF THE TURING MACHINE THEORY

A. Universal Turing Machines

More precisely, a universal Turing machine (UTM) can simulate the behavior of an arbitrary TM over any set of input symbols. Thus, it is possible to create a single machine that can be used to compute any computable sequence.

It leaves as part of its output a description of the simulated Turing machine tape as if the simulated machine had performed the calculation [7].

Figure 4 shows a graphical representation of the UTM. The universal machine has three pieces of information about the machine it is simulating: A basic description of the machine; The contents of the machine tape; the internal state of the machine. The Universal machine then simulates the machine by looking at the input on the tape and the state of the machine. The machine is controlled by changing its state based on the input. Thus, one machine runs another machine.

There are several definitions of UTMs, but only three (3) of them will be considered in this paper, as presented in [8].

Let α, β represent the configuration of a TM and $\beta \downarrow$ represent the final configuration of β . Let $\beta_1 \xrightarrow{M} \beta_2$ mean that TM M moves from a configuration β_1 to a configuration β_2 by one step and we write $\beta_1 \xrightarrow{M} \beta_j$ for $\beta_1 \xrightarrow{M} \beta_2 \xrightarrow{M} \dots \xrightarrow{M} \beta_j$. Let M be a fixed TM. Denote via B the set of all configurations of all Turing machines and denote via B_M the set of all configurations of M . It is well known that both B and B_M are recursive sets. Also, we define a function F_M as follows:

$$F_M(\alpha) = \beta \text{ if and only if } \alpha \xrightarrow{M} \beta, \quad (1)$$

where, $\alpha, \beta \in B_M$ and \downarrow . We denote the domain of F and the range of F with $Def(F)$ and $Val(F)$, respectively.

Definition 1: Let $\psi(n, x)$ be some universal partial recursive function for all partial recursive functions of one variable. A TM U is called universal (UTM), if there exists a total recursive (or simple-recursive) function $\rho(n, x)$, the coding

function with $Val(\rho) \subseteq B_u$, and a recursive function $\lambda(a)$, the decoding function, defined on the set B_u , so that for all Tn and x the following holds:

$$\lambda(F_u(\rho(n, x))) = \psi(n, x) \quad (2)$$

Definition 2: A TM M simulates the TM T , if there exists a recursive function $\tilde{\rho}(\alpha)$, the coding function, defined on the set B_T , with $Val(\tilde{\rho}) \subseteq B_M$ and a recursive function $\tilde{\lambda}(\alpha)$, the decoding function, defined on the set B_M , with $Val(\tilde{\lambda}) \subseteq B_T$, so that for all $\alpha \in B_T$, the following holds:

$$\tilde{\lambda}F_M(\tilde{\rho}(\alpha)) = F_T(\alpha) \quad (3)$$

Definition 3: A TM U is called a universal Turing machine if one can simulate each TM M and one can effectively get coding and decoding functions from the program of the TM M , i.e. there exists a recursive function $\tilde{\rho}(n, \alpha)$ defined on $N * B$ with $Val(\tilde{\rho}) \subseteq B_U$ and a recursive function $\tilde{\lambda}(n, \alpha)$ defined on $N * B_U$ with $Val(\tilde{\lambda}) \subseteq B$ so that for all $\langle n, \alpha \rangle \in N * B$ the following holds:

$$\tilde{\lambda}(F_U(\tilde{\rho}(n, \alpha))) = F_T(\alpha) \quad (4)$$

B. Small Universal Turing Machines

Small UTMs are TMs that have a relatively small number of states and symbols in their alphabet, making them more compact and efficient. A small standard UTM has a few key features:

- It has a minimal or near-minimal number of states and symbols in its alphabet, making it compact and efficient.
- It uses a standard encoding scheme for representing the target TM's description and input. This encoding is typically provided on the UTM's tape, allowing the UTM to read, interpret, and simulate the target TM.
- It can simulate the behaviour of any other TM, regardless of the number of states, symbols, or complexity of the target machine.

[9] posed the problem of the construction of the simplest UTM by considering an ordinary deterministic TM with a two-way infinite tape and one head [8]. [9], [10] showed that given any TM M , one can effectively construct a two-state TM M' which imitates the step-by-step behaviour of M . Since by using an enlarged alphabet one can store both state and symbol information in a given tape square, the problem reduces to showing how the state information of M can be transmitted from one square adjacent square to an adjacent square on the two-state TM M' .

Researchers have constructed various small UTMs over the years, with the aim of minimizing the number of states and symbols required for universality. The most recent small UTM which was constructed by [11] had state-symbol pairs of (5, 5), (6, 4), (9, 3) and (15, 2).

Table 1 shows the various small TMs which have been developed over the years, as presented in [12].

Fig. 4. Graphical representation of universal Turing machine

TABLE I
LIST OF SMALLEST STANDARD TURING MACHINES (BY STATE-SYMBOL PRODUCT)

State-Symbols Pairs	State-Symbol Product	Author
(m, 2), (2, n)	2m, 2	[9]
(7, 4)	28	[13]
(3, 10)	30	[14]
(7, 4), (5, 5), (4, 6), (10, 30)	28, 25, 24	[8], [14]
(7, 4)	28	[15]
(15, 2), (9, 3), (5, 5), (6,4)	30, 27, 25, 24	[11]

In [11], the authors introduced a variant of the TM based on bi-tag systems called the Clockwise TM. A clockwise Turing machine is a machine that has a single tape, which is circular, and whose tape head moves only in a clockwise direction. Formerly, a clockwise TM is a tuple $C = (Q, \Sigma, f, q_1, q_{|Q|})$. Q and Σ are the finite sets of states and tape symbols, respectively. $q_1 \in Q$ is the start state and $q_{|Q|} \in q$ is the halt state.

The transition function $f : Q * \Sigma \rightarrow \Sigma \cup \Sigma \Sigma * Q$ is undefined on state $q_{|Q|}$ and is defined for all $q \in Q, q \neq q_{|Q|}$. We write f as a list of clockwise transition rules. Each clockwise transition rule is a quadruple $t = (q_x, \sigma_1, v, q_y)$, with initial state q_x , read symbol σ_1 , write value $v \in \Sigma \cup \Sigma \Sigma$ and next state q_y .

C. Busy Beaver

A busy beaver is a TM that is designed to maximize the number of steps it takes to halt (i.e., the number of steps it runs before stopping or entering an infinite loop). The name "busy beaver" comes from the idea that the machine is "busy" working as hard as it can to produce the most output possible. The problem of determining the maximum number of steps a busy beaver with a given number of states can take before halting is uncomputable. This is because it can be used to solve the halting problem, which is known to be undecidable for TMs.

[16] defined a TM B as a k-state Busy Beaver if when run on the empty tape as input, B halts, and also runs for at least as many steps before halting as all other halting k-state Turing machines. In [16], the authors presented a 7,910-state TM whose behaviour is independent of ZFC (Zermelo-Fraenkel set theory with the axiom of choice). It is not possible to prove that such a machine halts or doesn't halt using the axioms of ZFC, assuming that a stronger set theory is consistent.

Definition: According to the Busy Beaver competition, [17], busy beaver M is defined as follows: Let $TM(k, l)$ be the set of TMs with $card(Q) = k$ states and $card(\Sigma) = l$ symbols. Then a machine in $TM(k, l)$ is given by a function from $Q * \Sigma$ to $(\Sigma * L, R * Q) \cup (1, R, H)$, so

$$cardTM(k, l) = (2kl + 1)^{kl} \quad (5)$$

Let Σ^* be the set of finite words from alphabet Σ , λ the empty word, $|x|$ the length of $x \in \Sigma^*$, and Σ^n the set of words with length n . If $x \in \Sigma^*$, then we define $x^0 = \lambda$, $x^1 = x$, and, for any $n \geq 1$, $x^{n+1} = x^n x$. An infinite to the right string of 0s is denoted by 0 , and an infinite to the left string of 0s, by ${}^\omega 0$. A configuration of machine M is a two-sided infinite string ${}^\omega 0x(Z_a)y0^\omega$, where $Z \in Q \cup H$, $a \in \Sigma, x, y \in \Sigma^*$. Then, the word $xay \in \Sigma^*$ is written on the tape, between two infinite strings of 0s, the state is Z and the head scans symbol a . The initial configuration of M on an input $x_1 x_2 \dots x_n \in \Sigma^*$ is

$${}^\omega 0(Ax_1)x_2 \dots x_n 0^\omega \quad (6)$$

IV. APPLICATION OF TURING MACHINES

A. Computational Biology

TMs are used in the analysis of biological data. They are used to model the behaviour of biological systems, such as DNA sequencing and protein folding. Another way TMs are

TABLE II
APPLICATIONS OF TMS, MERITS AND THEORITICAL CONCEPTS

Application	Stride (Merit)	Mathematical concepts used
Cryptography	Encryption algorithms based on the difficulty of factoring large numbers, which can be solved using a Turing Machine.	Number theory, modular arithmetic, and prime factorization
Artificial Intelligence	Neural networks, which can be modeled as Turing Machines, are used in many AI applications.	Linear algebra, calculus, and probability theory
Computer Science Theory	The Church-Turing thesis, which states that any computable function can be computed by a Turing Machine, has had a profound impact on computer science	Set theory, logic, and computability theory
Compiler Construction	Turing Machines have been used to help develop compilers, which are programs that translate high-level programming languages into machine code	Formal languages and automata theory
Natural Language Processing	Turing Machines have been used as the basis for language models, which are used in natural language processing applications	Probability theory, Markov models, and statistical learning
Quantum Computing	Quantum Turing Machines, which are based on the principles of quantum mechanics, can simulate any quantum algorithm and are used in the study of quantum complexity theory	Linear algebra, complex analysis, and quantum mechanics
Computational Biology	Turing Machines have been used in the modeling and analysis of biological systems, such as genetic networks and protein folding	Probability theory, differential equations, and graph theory
Complexity Theory	The concept of Turing completeness, which means that a system or programming language is capable of simulating any other Turing Machine, has been used to classify the computational complexity of problems	Computational complexity theory, Big O notation, and algorithms
Compiler Optimization	Turing Machines have been used to analyze and optimize compiler performance	Graph theory, optimization algorithms, and program analysis

applied is the use of DNA computing to implement a true Nondeterministic Universal Turing Machine (NUTM) [18].

Like other forms of molecular computing, DNA computing trades space for time: "There's plenty of room at the bottom". The goal of building a molecular scale UTM has been pursued for over 50 years, with the most common molecule suggested being DNA, but protein has also been proposed. DNA is an excellent medium for information processing and storage. It is very stable, as the sequencing of ancient DNA demonstrates. It can also reliably be copied, and many genes have remained virtually unchanged for billions of years. These properties give DNA computing potential advantages in speed, energy efficiency and information storage over electronics the number of operations for a desktop.

A DNA computer could plausibly be approximately 1020 (approx. 103 times faster than the fastest current supercomputer). It can execute approximately 2×10^{19} operations per joule (i.e., more than current supercomputers) and can utilize memory with an information density of approximately 1-bit nm³ (i.e., 108 denser than current memory). These advantages mean that it is feasible that a DNA NUTM-based computer could potentially utilize more processors than all the electronic computers in the world combined, and so outperforms all standard computers on significant practical problems.

B. Formal Semantics of Programming Languages

[19], proved that the Semantic Turing Machine (STM) can run assembler-like STM programs. Each memory command is understandable. The STM uses the dot operation to indicate semantic relations between nodes. Complex relations can be easily expressed as a directed, labelled graph or sparse matrix using the dot method. STMs provide natural semantic expression. TMs are used to define the formal semantics of programming languages. They are used to define the syntax

and semantics of programming constructs, such as loops, functions, and recursion. In Artificial Intelligence, TMs are used in the design and analysis of artificial intelligence and cryptographic algorithms. TMs can model the behaviour of intelligent agents, such as robots, autonomous vehicles, and virtual assistants as well as the behaviour of encryption and decryption algorithms to analyse their security properties.

q	σ	$\delta(q, \sigma)$
q_0	a	$(q_1, \#)$
q_0	$\#$	$(h, \#)$
q_1	a	(q_0, a)
q_1	$\#$	(q_0, \Rightarrow)

C. Design and Analysis of Compilers

TMs are extensively used in the design and analysis of compilers to model the behaviour of programming languages and to analyse the efficiency of code generation. The code lines below demonstrate how a TM may be encoded as a C++ template metaprogram – using a simple machine that replaces a string of a's with #'s and then halts:

$$K = \{q_0, q_1, h\}$$

$$\Sigma = \{a, \#\}$$

$$s = q_0$$

The states K and alphabet $\Sigma \cup \{\Leftarrow, \Rightarrow\}$ are encoded as empty C++ types:

```

/* States */
struct Halt
struct Q0
struct Q1

/* Alphabet */
struct Left {}
struct Right {}
struct Blank {}

```

```
/* Tape representation */  
struct Nil ;  
template<class Head, class Tail>  
struct Pair {  
typedef Head head;  
typedef Tail tail;  
};
```

D. Neural Turing Machine in Medicine

[20] indicated that working memory-like neural Turing machines may access data according to rules. Neural Turing Machine is a model, which was inspired by the working memory system in human cognition. It is a type of recurrent neural network with an external memory that allows it to access data based on certain rules. This makes it a powerful tool in the field of artificial intelligence, particularly, in the area of natural language processing and sequence learning. The neural TM has the potential to perform tasks that require both short-term memory and long-term memory. Its ability to learn abstract patterns and resolve cognitive problems makes it an effective method for multilayer neural network training, in combination with other deep learning techniques. The neural TM has opened up new avenues for the development of more advanced and efficient AI systems. Machine learning is revolutionizing healthcare. Machine learning has made a tangible difference in healthcare in different ways. According to a survey conducted by "Healthcare IT News," 63% of healthcare professionals asserted that AI had delivered enhanced value in pathology, pharma, radiology, and remote health monitoring. A wide array of machine learning applications continues to drive innovation and provide a sophisticated framework for healthcare solutions.

E. Virtual Assistants

Virtual assistants are increasingly used by many businesses and industries, including healthcare. [21], proposed the use of Cognitive Work Analysis and the Turing Machine Task Analysis (TMTA) method to guide the specification of remote assistance systems for medical emergencies occurring in remote locations. By conducting a work domain analysis of acute abdominal pain and formalizing a Turing machine state space based on medical knowledge, this method provides a global architecture of medical assistance for isolated caregivers and guidance to define the kind of assistance functions that could be implemented. The simulation of Turing machine scenarios helps specify medical assistance functions, while the abstraction hierarchy technique provides a model of the dynamics of interaction between agents and work domain within the framework of adaptive assistance. These virtual assistants can be deployed for collecting patient information, including details about demographic, insurance, financing, health history, data mining, procurement, and analysis of different records. Various chatbot virtual assistants help engage with the patients, reducing human effort and providing cost-efficient solutions for administrative tasks.

F. Data Privacy

The patient's data is extremely sensitive and confidential. There are often reports of this data getting breached by unethical elements. In [22], the authors proposed an algorithm that uses the decrement and increment conditions of the TM to encrypt and decrypt text. The algorithm converts the text into ASCII, then into binary and reverses it. The binary value is then decremented and an 8-bit string is generated. A 4-digit number is used for division and the remainder and quotient are added with required padding to create a cipher text. The algorithm aims to provide a data security solution using the principles of the TT. These TM principles can also implement additional layers of security for sensitive data, thus, ensuring high levels of data privacy with minimal risks of breaches.

The use of mathematical concepts in conjunction with the theoretical framework of TMs have allowed for numerous strides and advancements in a variety of fields, from cryptography to artificial intelligence to computational biology. Table 2 presents a systematic overview of the applications of TMs, their merits and associated mathematical concepts deployed.

V. CONCLUSION

The paper has provided a more concise and systematic overview of the evolution of the TM model since its inception. It discussed the formal definition of TMs, UTMs and their variants, small TMs and the busy beaver machine. Additionally, the fundamental concepts of TMs in theoretical computer science and their applications in various fields such as artificial intelligence, cryptography, computational biology, compiler design, game theory, and natural language processing have been synthesized.

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